

Building Roadmaps to Industrial
Decarbonisation and Green Economy
through EU-China Cooperation

D7.3 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan – Update 1

WP7 – Open & FAIR science, Mutual Learning,
Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the Description of the Action (DoA)

The I2AM PARIS web platform is now referred as IAM PARIS web platform. No other changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as a reference document among consortium partners to support the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the project.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report is the first update of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) plan of EU-CHINA BRIDGE to relevant audiences. The report starts by defining the objectives of the CDE strategy and Key Performance Indicators that will be used for the project's promotion activities and by reporting progress towards these indicators during the first half of the project. The report then identifies the target audiences and stakeholder groups of the project and suggests potential promotional channels and communication materials to reach them. During the first 18 months of the project, we have developed the website, established the visual identity, promoted the project in social media, created blogposts, and published the initial project outputs as four scientific publications, while organising several workshops for stakeholder engagement and capacity development. Nevertheless, the bulk of CDE activities will come towards the second half of the project, where most of the key exploitable results of the project are expected to be released. The report concludes with next steps for improving communication and dissemination activities in the coming months.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

History of changes

Date/Version	Status	Changes
23.09.2025	Deliverable for review	Initial version
30.09.2025	Finalised and submitted	Adapted the section on co-creation workshops and stakeholder dialogues; updated the number of conferences.

Preface

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries, co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways, and developing the most updated and comprehensive emissions data. It will intensively engage relevant stakeholders from both regions, enhancing dialogues, and fostering mutual learning among policymakers, industries, and experts. It will deliver two open-source EU-China joint technology inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron & steel and chemical industries, two co-implemented demonstrations of promising technologies in China, and co-created scale-up paths and roadmaps of the selected industrial technologies in both regions. It will also develop the most up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived climate pollutant emission inventories as well as dynamic monitoring of key emission sources at high spatiotemporal granularity. A state-of-the-art modelling framework will be developed, exploiting and advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China, using the latest emissions data, representing technology and policy options, enabling assessment of socioeconomic impacts, covering multiple economic sectors and regions, and offering high spatial and technology detail. The enhanced models will be used to co-produce net-zero pathways for the EU and China, explicitly assessing co-benefits and trade-offs of climate policies with other societal goals while exploring cooperation policies and governance to drive the global transformation and assessing the distributional and global-level implications of the two regions' decarbonisation. The pathways will be documented in new workspaces in the IAM PARIS platform.

WI – Wuppertal Institut fuer Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH	DE	
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	GR	
IIASA – Internationales Institut fuer angewandte Systemanalyse	AT	
UoB – The University of Birmingham	UK	
ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems	GR	
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	GR	
ITE – University of Kassel	DE	
THU-SA – Tsinghua University	CN	
THU-CE – Department of Chemical Engineering, Tsinghua University	CN	
THU-DESS – Department of Earth System Science, Tsinghua University	CN	
RUC – Renmin University of China	CN	
SDU – Shandong University	CN	
CHINACOAL – China National Coal Group Corporation	CN	
BITARIM – Advanced Research Institute of Multidisciplinary Sciences, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	
FULONG – Inner Mongolia Fulong Heating Engineering Technology Co., LTD	CN	
BIT-ME – School of Mechanical Engineering, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	

Executive Summary

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries and by co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways. This report describes the first update of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) strategy of the project for promoting all these results to key stakeholders.

The report starts by an introduction to the project and its research outputs. These outputs include two open-source EU-China joint technology inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron, steel, and chemical industries, improved climate pollutant emission inventories, and a state-of-the-art modelling framework, advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China. Based on these outputs, the report delineates the objectives of the CDE strategy as well as the Key Performance Indicators that are set for the project's promotion activities.

In order to fulfil these objectives, the CDE plan then discusses the target audiences and outlines communication channels and materials to share project results so that they are openly available and easily accessible to everyone. Additionally, the plan describes a list of methods and materials tailored to each target group, such as policy briefs for policymakers, scientific publications for scientists, and synergies and collaborations for other EU projects.

During the first 18 months of the project we have developed the website, established the visual identity, promoted the project in social media, created blogposts, and published the initial project outputs as four scientific publications, while organising several workshops for stakeholder engagement and capacity development. Nevertheless, the bulk of CDE activities will come towards the second half of the project, where most of the key exploitable results of the project are expected to be released.

The current stage of CDE activities is also reflected to our progress towards the communication and dissemination KPIs. Specifically, the target on the visual identity has been already reached, while there is already progress towards our targets for social media, newsletters, scientific outreach, media articles/blog items, and synergies with other projects. Conversely, we will need to strengthen our efforts in all other metrics by promoting our project website to increase its visitors and by developing more infographics, videos, policy briefs, and content for the IAM PARIS platform. The report concludes with next steps for improving communication and dissemination activities in the coming months.

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1 Introduction

EU-CHINA BRIDGE supports the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries, co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways, and developing the most updated and comprehensive emissions data. In order to achieve these goals, the project engages with relevant stakeholders from both regions, enhancing dialogues, and fostering mutual learning among policymakers, industries, and experts.

By the project's end, we will deliver:

- two open-source EU-China joint technology and policy inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron & steel and chemical industries;
- two co-implemented demonstrations of promising technologies in China;
- co-created scale-up paths and roadmaps of the selected industrial technologies in both regions;
- up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived climate pollutant emission inventories;
- a state-of-the-art modelling framework, advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China, using the latest emissions inventories;
- co-produced net-zero pathways for the EU and China using the new modelling framework.

Towards these efforts, we have established and maintained regular interactions with stakeholders and interested parties to ensure the successful co-creation, dissemination, and exploitation of project results. This report describes the first update of the strategy for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of information and results of the project to relevant audiences. Overall, the CDE plan has the following objectives:

1. communicating project results and successful practices to demonstrate the project's impact to a wider audience in EU and China;
2. creating the means to disseminate results to stakeholders, including policymakers, industries, and the scientific community, motivating them to exploit project results;
3. promoting the exploitation potential of the project's flagship outputs, both during and beyond the project life.

These objectives are described in detail in Chapter 2, along with a detailed reporting of monitored CDE activities and their key performance indicators (KPIs). In order to fulfil these objectives, the CDE plan also discusses the target audiences and their characteristics and outlines communication channels to share project results so that they are openly available and easily accessible to everyone. Additionally, the plan describes a list of methods tailored to each target group, such as communication materials for the general public, policy briefs for policymakers, as well as external conferences and synergies and collaborations with other EU projects for academic dissemination. As part of the first update of the CDE plan, we also report our progress towards these indicators during the first half of the project.

In summary, the CDE plan is structured based on the following questions on the promotion process:

- **To whom?** Identification of the audiences to which the project will be promoted (Chapter 3).

- **How?** Selection of appropriate promotional channels and reporting of our progress by Month 18 of the project (Chapter 4).
- **What?** Planning and implementation of the CDE activities (Chapter 5 for communication materials and Chapter 6 for an overview of current progress along with next steps on improving promotion efforts).

2 Goals and targets of the CDE plan

2.1 The three pillars of promotion: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

Communication is the process of informing the widest possible audience, including the media and the wider public, regarding the project and its results. EU-CHINA BRIDGE is mainly communicated as a joint effort between researchers from the EU and China, focused on jointly developing advanced technology roadmaps and conducting in-depth analyses of policies and governance related to industrial decarbonization in both regions, overall net-zero strategies, and the most up-to-date greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions data. This collaborative aspect comes at a key time where regional rivalries monopolise the news. Thus, the main communication message of EU-CHINA BRIDGE would be that collaborations between the research communities of EU and China can be successful and can lead to benefits and solutions for the transition of both regions. We will also emphasise the need for decarbonisation pathways with a more inter-regional perspective, especially in the industrial decarbonisation that is strongly interrelated to global trade and supply chains.

Dissemination is the process of transferring produced knowledge and results to enable others to use and exploit them. Dissemination focuses on the results of the initiative, rather than the initiative itself, as well on how the outcomes can be exploited by interested parties. The main audiences suitable for dissemination are the ones who could use the results in their operation. Policymakers from China and the EU (from both national and regional levels) are a natural target audience for project outcomes such as the modelled net-zero pathways and technology roadmaps. Industrial decision-makers are also interested in the scaling-up paths, technology roadmaps, and pathways and in their impacts on and requirements from industry. Modelling researchers and social scientists are also important audiences, as the project aims to strengthen the dialogue between Chinese and European experts, improve the quality and accuracy of their models, and enhance the integration of SSH into modelling, through mutual learning and exchange. Lastly, NGOs and international climate and sustainable development organisations can be also interested in the industrial technology roadmaps and EU and China net-zero pathways due to common interests.

Exploitation is the effective practical use of project results through scientific, economic, political, or societal routes of utilisation. The objective of exploitation is to go one step further than dissemination and turn research and innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society. Thus, the main audiences of exploitation are the same as the ones suitable for dissemination. Examples of successful exploitation activities include policymakers using project findings to inform their climate strategies and industrial decarbonisation policies and industrial actors using the technology roadmaps to inform their strategic planning.

2.2 Overall Targets

Creating a living document

The CDE plan will be periodically updated throughout the project and specifically on Month 18 and 36. Apart from these reports, we will continuously monitor all CDE activities through an online CDE tracker where each consortium member can add events organised by the project, external events where project partners represent the project, and social media posts on the project's account. The CDE tracker also tracks useful metrics such as the views of the posts and the number of participants in the events. A similar tracker also monitors the development, publication, and dissemination of scientific articles, deliverables, policy briefs, and other written

outputs of the project¹.

Customising information to target audiences

The CDE strategy uses a customised approach to successfully communicate the project's key messages to its various target groups based on the audience segmentation that is initially selected (see Chapter 3). Accordingly, the WP7 team creates distinct core messages for each group and link them with appropriate communication channels. Each target audience has formal and informal channels for communication (e.g., scientific publications versus scientific groups in LinkedIn). Therefore, in addition to being mindful of the language used, it is important to consider communication style and tone. While the essential scientific content will stay unchanged, communication initiatives will be adapted for the various stakeholder groups and communication channels.

Adopting an inclusive and gender-sensitive approach

The CDE team will strive to reach good balance of stakeholders of different genders, ages, and backgrounds in its communication and dissemination activities. Gender will be a focal point in EU-CHINA BRIDGE and will be factored in the modelling activities of the project by, e.g., analysing gender implications of pathways to net zero. The gender dimension will be also considered in the policy analysis of industrial waste heat utilisation (IWHU) for district heating. Furthermore, gender will be further emphasised in Co-Creation Workshops (WP1) and Stakeholder Dialogues (WP7). We will ensure that stakeholder representation in these events is gender-balanced and strive to achieve a gender balance with at least 50% representation of women in stakeholder groups, which will be considered as a part of the design, planning and organisation of these events (e.g., attendance at events, keynote addresses, setting agendas, etc.).

Planning for a travelling restriction-resilient CDE

Due to uncertainties related to major global disturbances such as an eventual resurgence of COVID-19 or another pandemic, appropriate methodological alternatives have been identified to ensure that the co-creation, dissemination, and communication activities can continue. While online meetings and communication have become common during the last years, for the sake of building trust with the project team and with external stakeholders, physical events will still be used when possible. In cooperation with the project coordinator, the CDE team will constantly monitor major global disturbances and decide when each methodological alternative will be used. Table 1 shows activities that are identified as potentially vulnerable to such disturbances, along with their methodological alternatives.

Table 1. Project activities that can be potentially affected by travelling restrictions

Activity	Preferred implementation	Methodological alternatives
Co-creation Workshops, Stakeholder Dialogues, Capacity building and training events	In-person and virtual workshops	Only virtual workshops, carefully designed to reduce video-call fatigue and secure time for discussion and input from all participants

¹<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1GiTyMg6mNqRemy3aYwLJKxyB7K2o8xB/edit?usp=sharing&oid=100626678533933877508&rtpof=true&sd=true>

Annual project meetings among consortium partners	In-person meetings (hybrid)	Online meetings through Microsoft Teams, Zoom, or Google Meet)
Conferences, pitch meetings with policymakers, and other communication and dissemination activities	In-person and online activities	Only online through Microsoft Teams, Zoom, or Google Meet

Supporting open access

Unless they are marked as confidential, all deliverables will be uploaded in the project website and Zenodo with a Creative Commons open-access license². Similarly, we will also strive to make new model code available in GitHub using open-source licensing. Regarding scientific publications, we will prioritise not only high-impact but also fully open-access journals offering, when feasible, open peer review, such as Open Research Europe which will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of participating organisations. Access to supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated Zenodo community³, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability.

Going paper-free

The CDE strategy is designed to be as paper-free as possible. Printed material will be used sparingly and only when deemed necessary to the CDE activity at hand such as on physical events. However, visual identity templates and communication materials will be provided openly on the website (see Chapter 5)⁴, allowing any interested party to download and use them.

2.3 Monitored CDE activities and indicators

To ensure that project results are successfully communicated and disseminated, a set of key performance indicators have been set and presented in Tables 2 and 3, along with expected audiences and monitoring tools. Progress towards these targets will be monitored on a regular basis, to confirm that the project is on track to achieve them or to take corrective measures if necessary. The communication channels and materials to achieve these targets are detailed in Chapters 4 and 5 respectively. These chapters also report our progress in terms of using these communication channels and creating new materials. This progress is summarised in Chapter 6 along with lessons learned and suggestions for improvement.

Table 2. Monitored communication activities and suggested KPIs

Activity	Objective	Expected audience and KPIs	Monitoring tool
Visual identity	Create visually compelling material for stakeholders in the EU and China	All stakeholder groups: policy, industry, research, civil society	All materials will be published on the project website

² This mandate concerns European partners; partners in China shall consider releasing code as open source but are not mandated by their funding agency.

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-china-bridge>

⁴ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/communication/visual-identity>

Project website	Present the project, disseminate its outcomes, and serve as an online library of all project publications	All stakeholder groups: 2000 unique visitors/year 30% of return visitors	Google Analytics
Social media	Create familiarity with the project, share results among scientists, policy, industry, citizens, and other groups	All stakeholder groups: 1,000 uses of EU-CHINA BRIDGE hashtag or handle, 500 followers on LinkedIn/Twitter 1000 on WeChat	Analytics of social media platforms
Newsletters (four per year)	Involve stakeholders in the progress of the project; share news, commentaries, and project outcomes	All stakeholder groups: 3000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate	Email monitoring system; Website download analytics
Infographics & videos	Explain pertinent concepts and outcomes of the project	Industry, society, policymakers: >1,000 views/downloads	YouTube/Instagram stats; # downloads
Media articles	Explain major outcomes of the project via non-technical language.	Civil society: At least 5 articles	Links of articles shared on website

Table 3. Monitored dissemination activities and suggested KPIs

Activity	Objective	Expected audience and KPIs	Monitoring tool
Enhanced I²AM PARIS platform	Facilitating harmonisation /modelling; fostering co-creation; validating modelling results	All stakeholder groups: 2000 unique users/year 30% of return visitors	Google Analytics
Policy briefs	Inform EU and Chinese policymakers and industry decision-makers	Policymakers, industry: 12 policy briefs	Number of briefs
Scientific outreach	Disseminate project results in academic outlets	Academia: > 15 papers; > 6 conferences	Digital monitoring, OpenAIRE entries
Networking activities with relevant EU and Chinese projects	Share results among different research communities and create synergies with projects under similar topics	Academia: Project referenced in 10 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	Digital monitoring, # of joint papers & acknowledged projects in papers

Additionally, several project tasks are directly related to dissemination and exploitation objectives of the project such as the co-creation work of WP1 and the capacity building events of Task 7.5 of WP7. Table 4

presents all such tasks that were identified at the project's inception stage. While the CDE project team (mainly including members of HOLISTIC) is not directly involved in most of these tasks, it will nevertheless support project partners in these activities as they see fit, e.g., promoting the capacity development workshops etc. Further relevant tasks may be added in the table as the project is evolving.

Table 4. WPs and tasks that are directly related to dissemination and exploitation objectives

WP/Tasks	Dissemination & exploitation objectives	Activities	Month
WP1	Fostering direct productive co-creation workshops with stakeholders	Mapping stakeholders; interviews in-person & online workshops	1-30
WPs 3, 4, 6	Ensuring comprehensibility of the results, tailoring them to the needs of policymakers and industrial stakeholders	Discussing results with stakeholders, Drafting of Policy briefs	8-34
Task 7.2	Reaching out a broader audience of stakeholders and experts; Inform policymakers and industrial, and other stakeholders on the project findings and promote their exploitation	Stakeholder dialogues at multiple levels (with the EU and China, between the EU and China, international)	9-36
Tasks 7.4, 7.6	Expansion of the IAM PARIS platform, establishing it as a vessel of the EU and international modelling community	Enhanced IAM PARIS platform: updated model information, workspaces, insights, diagnostics, protocols; open science principles; FAIR data	7-36
Task 7.5	Building capacity of model and data researchers in the EU and China and globally	Training workshops for researchers EU, China, and globally, online workshops, open-source data and modelling tools	6-36
WP2-6	Engaging with the wider academic community	Open access online dataset, papers to scientific journals, individual conference contributions, concerted conference sessions	6-36

3 Target audiences

For implementing successful and impactful CDE activities, it is crucial to have a thorough awareness of the interests and motivations of the stakeholders that are considered as target audiences for the project. As EU-CHINA BRIDGE aims to engage with diverse audiences in the EU and China, the CDE team aims to understand the characteristics of potentially interested parties, facilitate tailored communication, and implement different engagement strategies for each audience. Since most of the members of the CDE team are coming from the EU, we have and will strive to closely cooperate with the Chinese partners and participate in engagement events with Chinese stakeholders in order to understand the context and relevant audiences for that region. Table 5 shows the target audiences that have been identified at the project's inception, along with relevant communication methods for each audience.

Table 5. Target audiences and relevant communication/dissemination methods

Target audiences	Examples of stakeholders	Relevant methods
Scientists, Researchers, Academia	<p>Modelers working with integrated assessment models and climate-economy models in general</p> <p>Researchers working on climate change mitigation topics</p> <p>Industrial ecology scientists</p> <p>Researchers on international governance and collaboration topics</p>	<p>Scientific publications and project deliverables</p> <p>Scientific conferences (e.g., international conferences such as IAMC, EU conferences such as ECEMP, and other relevant modelling-relevant events in China)</p> <p>Social media posts</p> <p>Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube)</p> <p>Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues</p> <p>Capacity building and training events</p> <p>IAM PARIS platform</p>
Horizon Europe projects, European, Chinese, and international modelling consortia	<p>Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium</p> <p>European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum</p> <p>H2020 PARIS REINFORCE</p> <p>H2020 NDC ASPECTS</p> <p>HEU IAM COMPACT</p> <p>HEU DIAMOND</p>	<p>Participation in project clustering events</p> <p>Participation in modelling conferences and meetings</p> <p>Mailing lists and newsletters</p> <p>Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues</p> <p>IAM PARIS platform</p>
Policymakers at all scales	European Commission	<p>Policy briefs</p> <p>Policy-relevant conferences and events (e.g.,</p>

	<p>European Parliament National EU governments Chinese government officials EU-China flagship initiative on Climate Change and Biodiversity</p>	<p>COP meetings, EU Sustainable Energy Week, EU Green Week) Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues IAM PARIS platform</p>
<p>Industry decision-makers</p>	<p>World steel association CEFIC IEA Thyssenkrupp COVESTRO BASF China Energy Reserve and Chemicals Group Company China Energy Investment World Business Council for Sustainable Development</p>	<p>Industry-relevant events Social media posts in LinkedIn Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues Policy briefs IAM PARIS platform</p>
<p>Civil society and NGOs</p>	<p>Steel and chemical associations in the EU, China, and globally WWF, Greenpeace, WRI, GIZ</p>	<p>Social media posts News articles Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues</p>
<p>Media</p>	<p>The Conversation The Manufacturer South China Morning Post RENEW Industry EURACTIV Carbon Brief Climatechangemitigation.eu ClimateChangePost Dialogue Earth</p>	<p>Press releases News articles</p>

Based on the experience of the WP7 team with previous Horizon projects relating to energy and climate

modelling (e.g., H2020 PARIS REINFORCE, H2020 NDC ASPECTS, HEU IAM COMPACT, HEU DIAMOND), an initial list of stakeholders has been identified for each of the target audience categories. Examples of these stakeholders can be seen in Table 5, while for media outlets a more complete list can be found on the project's Google Drive. Stakeholder lists will be further enhanced through relevant contacts of all project partners, newsletter subscribers, and invitees in engagement events. In line with the rules of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), exchanging sensitive information about the stakeholders between partner organisations in the consortium will be avoided, unless explicit consent is provided by a stakeholder. Each partner organisation will be in charge of establishing and maintaining contact with their own stakeholders, under the coordination of the CDE team.

4 Promotional channels

At the heart of the CDE plan is the design and implementation of promotional channels to reach target audiences, disseminate messages and outputs, and ensure their exploitation. The promotional channels are the routes through which the messages from the project find their relevant audiences, including the project website and the IAM PARIS platform, posts on social media, participation in conferences and others. These channels are then used to distribute communication means that encapsulate messages from the project, i.e., publications, infographics, or videos. Each combination of promotional channels and means has a particular function and level of promotion. For instance, a scientific publication contains technical details that aim to provide scientists, modellers, and researchers with a more in-depth view of the project's outcome. On the other hand, an infographic is better suited to showcase the project's concept and results to a broader audience, whereas a policy brief is providing actionable and policy-relevant findings from the project to decision makers.

4.1 Project website

The project website is online and can be publicly accessed at <https://eu-china-bridge.eu>. It will serve as a one-stop-shop for EU-CHINA BRIDGE, providing comprehensive information about the project and the consortium team, news and updates, as well as links to all project outputs including deliverables, publications, and conference slides. In addition, the website will be continuously updated throughout the project's duration and will stay online at least two years after the end of the project. Figure 1 showcases the homepage of the website.

Figure 1. Homepage of the project website (upper part)

The website is designed in line with the project's colour palette, logo, and the overall visual identity and has been developed using the open-source Drupal framework (version 10). Apart from being open source, Drupal was selected as it offers a powerful Content Management System (CMS), packing many features and extensions that can improve the website's responsiveness to a wide range of devices (mobiles, laptops, desktops), its security, and its accessibility to a wide variety of audiences. The website is provided in English while a project description is also translated in Chinese⁵. A reference to the IAM PARIS⁶ platform will be also added, linking the website with the modelling documentation and result workspaces that will be developed for EU-CHINA BRIDGE. The news and material updated on the website will also serve as a content for a bilingual newsletter sent to interested stakeholders at least four times per year.

In terms of evaluating its performance, we aim to have more than 2,000 unique visitors per year, with 30% of them being return visitors. These indicators will be measured through the project's Google Analytics account which is already set up and connected to the project website. Aiming to increase its visibility, the website will be continuously promoted through the other communication and dissemination channels of the project such as social media and newsletters. The website will be maintained during the project's duration, while all updates will be installed to ensure the website's security and performance.

Progress by M18: Within the last 12 months of the project, the project website had around 400 unique visitors with 10% of them being return visitors. This is understandable since the promotional content was limited during the first 1,5 year of the project, as most research activities have not yet produced their key outcomes. Visitors are expected to improve and reach our targets during the second half of the project, where project results will significantly increase.

4.2 The IAM PARIS platform

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will provide new content and functionalities to the IAM PARIS platform⁷, an open-access, data exchange platform for climate-economy modelling. This platform was developed, validated, and used in Horizon 2020 PARIS REINFORCE, enhanced in NDC ASPECTS, as well as further expanded currently in a series of Horizon Europe projects, such as IAM COMPACT and DIAMOND.

The EU-CHINA BRIDGE website will be cross-linked to the IAM PARIS platform, where all project models and modelling capabilities will be documented and dynamically presented, providing stakeholders with access to digestible information on each model and an overview of what they can and cannot do. It will thus allow stakeholders to understand assumptions and scenario elements (Task 6.1) and understand how different factors influence transitions and the interactions between the EU and Chinese pathways to climate neutrality (Task 6.4), essentially underpinning our co-creation activities (WP1). The platform will also provide interactive visualisations to scenario modelling results (Tasks 6.2-6.3) using different kinds of workspaces for expert and non-expert audiences. For instance, we will use a policy dashboard functionality that is available in the IAM PARIS platform, using policy questions to structure project results and make them more relevant.

The platform will also serve as a collection of all data products produced during the project, including links to repositories of new model code (WP5), to complete datasets of scenario results (WP6), to newly developed emissions inventories (WP2), and to technology inventories and roadmaps (WP3). These products will be accompanied with documents such as deliverables, scientific publications, and technical documents to provide

⁵ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/xiangmubeijinghemubiao>

⁶ <https://iamparis.eu/>

⁷ <https://iamparis.eu/>

detailed insights into our modelling capacities, applications, key assumptions, and limitations.

Progress by M18: A dedicated space has been created for EU-CHINA BRIDGE within the IAM PARIS platform (Figure 2) and is ready to accept information about the project's models as well as modelling results. An interactive explorer of the technology inventories of WP3 has been already added to the platform⁸ (Figure 3). More content is expected during the second half of the project.

Figure 2. EU-CHINA BRIDGE domain within IAM PARIS

Figure 3. Screenshot from the Technology Inventories interactive explorer in IAM PARIS

⁸ https://iamparis.eu/datastories/tech_inventories

4.3 Social media

Social media are online forums and platforms to exchange/share thoughts, opinions, knowledge, and expertise with a large audience and can be also used to host marketing, advertising efforts, and promotional campaigns. Apart from the website, social media channels will be key for both the communication and dissemination of the project. Overall, we have created and using dedicated EU-CHINA BRIDGE accounts on X⁹ (formerly known as Twitter), LinkedIn¹⁰, and BlueSky¹¹. Each of these accounts serve a different purpose: X and BlueSky are used for communication to the general public and stakeholders from the scientific and policy communities, the LinkedIn account will target more business and industrial stakeholders. Links for all channels are also provided on a concise webpage hosted by Linktree¹², as shown in Figure 4. The Linktree webpage is also accessible by a QR code (also shown in Figure 4) that is placed in all visual materials of the project in order to provide to their readers fast access to all social media channels at once.

Figure 4. List of all social media channels, website, and platforms of the project on Linktree

While in the project's Grant Agreement we have suggested to create an account in Mastodon, from our experience with the communication of similar research projects (e.g., H2020 NDC ASPECTS), we have concluded that this channel is not as effective as we have initially believed when we were writing the proposal for EU-CHINA BRIDGE. In contrast, BlueSky is considered much more effective in scientific communication in

⁹ https://x.com/eu_china_bridge

¹⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-china-bridge>

¹¹ <https://bsky.app/profile/eu-china-bridge.bsky.social>

¹² <https://linktr.ee/euchinabridge>

our field as many members of relevant scientific groups of Twitter (e.g., #energytwitter) have started using this platform. In terms of WeChat, we have refrained from creating a new dedicated account for EU-CHINA BRIDGE based on the suggestion of our Chinese partners. Instead, forward news and materials to our partners to publish in their own personal and institutional WeChat accounts, ensuring thus a receptive and relevant audience from the onset of our communication.

Progress by M18: We have gained 304 followers on LinkedIn and 137 on X, moving thus closely towards the target of having 500 followers on LinkedIn and X. Similarly, we had 105 uses of the #EU_China_Bridge hashtag or project handle (incl. reposts) and 520 interactions in LinkedIn (likes and reposts), showing that our social media accounts are gaining traction towards achieving the target of 1,000 total interactions with our hashtag/handle. Follower numbers are much better in BlueSky where we have reached 624.

4.4 News websites and blogs

Media websites and blogs can be also used to communicate and disseminate project outputs to a wide audience. The first version of the CDE plan provided an indicative list of high-calibre media websites that could be used for promoting project results including The Conversation¹³, EURACTIV¹⁴, The Guardian¹⁵, South China Morning Post¹⁶, ClimateChangePost¹⁷, ClimateChangeNews.com¹⁸, Euronews – Climate Now¹⁹, the Research*eu Results magazine²⁰, and Dialogue Earth²¹. Detailed descriptions of these media along with first ideas of content that could be provided from our project are also given in the first CDE plan²².

Progress by M18: No media articles haven been published yet in external news websites and blogs. Nevertheless, three blog items about different project activities have been already published in the blog of our project website²³. More details on these articles are given in Section 5.2.4.

4.5 Online collaboration and sharing platforms

Similar to the media websites in the previous section, the first version of the CDE plan include a list of relevant platforms for disseminating project results such as climatechangemitigation.eu²⁴, Capacity4Dev²⁵, and the IISD SDG Knowledge Hub²⁶. To these platforms we can now add the IAMC news²⁷ that is a platform for sharing new from the Integrated Assessment Modelling community.

Progress by M18: No articles haven been shared yet with these platforms. However, we are planning to share

¹³ <https://theconversation.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.euractiv.com/>

¹⁵ <https://www.theguardian.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.scmp.com>

¹⁷ <https://www.climatechangepost.com/>

¹⁸ <https://climatechangenews.com>

¹⁹ <https://www.euronews.com/green/green-series/climate-now>

²⁰ https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html

²¹ <https://dialogue.earth/en/climate/introducing-dialogue-earth/>

²² https://eu-china-bridge.eu/sites/default/files/2024-10/D7.1_EU_CHINA_BRIDGE_CDE.pdf

²³ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/news-events>

²⁴ <https://climatechangemitigation.eu>

²⁵ <https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/>

²⁶ <http://sdg.iisd.org/>

²⁷ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/news-jobs/news-from-the-community/>

soon an update on the technology inventories from WP3²⁸ with the IAMC community as these data would be useful for modelling industrial decarbonisation measures in other IAMs as well.

4.6 Data repositories and platforms

The first version of the CDE plan provided examples of data repositories and platforms that could be used for storing the results of EU-CHINA BRIDGE such as Zenodo²⁹, GitHub³⁰, OpenAIRE³¹, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)³².

Progress by M18: EU-CHINA BRIDGE has already established a community in Zenodo³³ (see Figure 5 for a screenshot), where we are continuously upload project publications and data as they become available. The Zenodo community is serving as a repository of all project's outputs to ensure the sustainability of project work even after the website will be suspended (two years after the end of the project).

The screenshot displays the Zenodo community interface for 'EU-CHINA BRIDGE - Building Roadmaps to Industrial Decarbonisation and Green Economy through EU-China Cooperation'. The page features a search bar, navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard', and a 'Log in / Sign up' button. The main content area shows a list of 15 results found, sorted by 'Newest'. The list includes three publications:

- September 3, 2025 (v1)** - Journal article - Open: **Global methane footprints growth and drivers 1990-2023** by Shan, Yuli; Tian, Kailian; Li, Ruoli; and 4 others. Description: Methane has been identified as the second-largest contributor to climate change, accounting for approximately 30% of global warming. Countries have established targets and are implementing various measures to curb methane emissions. However, our understanding of the trends in methane emissions and their drivers remains limited, particularly from a consumption... Part of EU Open Research Repository, EU-CHINA BRIDGE - Building Roadmaps to Industrial Decarbonisation and Green Economy through EU-China Cooperation. Uploaded on September 9, 2025 | Published in: Nature Communications, 2025. (3 views, 4 downloads)
- July 24, 2025 (v1)** - Journal article - Open: **Comparing economic impacts of net-zero transition with climate damage uncertainties using a dual-model approach** by Hartvig, Áron Dénes; Simo, Marton; Fazekas, Dora; and 4 others. Description: This study conducts a scenario analysis of global net-zero emissions by 2050 using two macroeconomic models with distinct theoretical foundations: E3ME (non-equilibrium) and GEM-E3 (equilibrium). The analysis quantifies the economic impacts of increasing climate policy ambition to meet the global 1.5 °C warming target and highlights key differences between the models... Part of EU Open Research Repository, ENTICE - Enhanced Understanding of Trade Impacts on Climate, Industries, and the Environment, EU-CHINA BRIDGE - Building Roadmaps to Industrial Decarbonisation and Green Economy through EU-China Cooperation. Uploaded on September 9, 2025. (5 views, 7 downloads)
- November 16, 2025 (v1)** - Journal article - Open: **Consumption-Based Emissions of African Countries: An Analysis of Decoupling Dynamics and Drivers** by Wang, Jieyu; Shan, Yuli; Xu, Jinghang; and 3 others. Description: Formulating equitable climate policies should not overlook the challenges faced by less developed regions. African countries are at a crucial stage of economic development and deeper integration into global trade. Therefore, understanding their carbon footprints (i.e., consumption-based CO2 emissions) is essential for crafting a sustainable development pathway for Africa... Part of EU Open Research Repository, EU-CHINA BRIDGE - Building Roadmaps to Industrial Decarbonisation and Green Economy through EU-China Cooperation. Uploaded on September 9, 2025. (4 views, 6 downloads)

Figure 5. Screenshot of EU-CHINA BRIDGE community in Zenodo

Similarly, we will upload new model code on GitHub, either to the GitHub organisations of the different modelling teams or directly to the IAM PARIS organisation³⁴. Also, we are already using the ARGOS service of

²⁸ https://iamparis.eu/datastories/tech_inventories

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org>

³⁰ <https://github.com>

³¹ <https://www.openaire.eu>

³² <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

³³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-china-bridge/>

³⁴ <https://github.com/i2amparis>

OpenAIRE³⁵ for creating a machine-actionable data management plan (see also Deliverable D7.7) and we will consider using some services from the European Open Science Cloud as well.

4.7 Partners' websites/blogs

Most consortium partners have websites featuring news on their research activities. On these websites, articles on the progress of EU-CHINA BRIDGE and announcements on recent reports or upcoming events can be published. Partner websites that could be used in the future for dissemination and communication include the websites of WI³⁶, E3M³⁷, IIASA³⁸, UoB³⁹, ICCS⁴⁰, HOL⁴¹, ITE⁴², THU-SA⁴³, THU-CE⁴⁴, THU-DESS⁴⁵, RUC⁴⁶, SDU⁴⁷, CHINACOAL⁴⁸, BITARIM⁴⁹, FULONG⁵⁰, and BIT-ME⁵¹. Project activities could also be promoted through partners' social media accounts and newsletters. The CDE team will keep consortium partners informed about project updates and encourage them to forward and promote these updates to their communication departments.

Progress by M18: Several project partners reposted our social media posts on LinkedIn⁵² and elsewhere. The dissemination through the newsletters and websites of our project partners will intensify during the second part of the project where more content will become available.

4.8 Peer-to-peer mailing lists

Peer-to-peer (P2P) mailing lists are subscription-based email services that enable individuals interested in specific topics to communicate with each other and exchange opinions and project results. P2P lists of project-related topics such as energy, IAMs, and climate change mitigation can help reach audiences from academia, policymaking, and business since most subscribers are actively working in sectors affected by these topics. Examples of these lists include the lists hosted by the International Institute for Sustainable Development⁵³. These lists will be used to disseminate the project's progress and output (newsletters, press releases, and general announcements) and invite subscribers to participate in the project's co-creation events. Additionally, these mailing lists will be used to follow research and novelties from project-relevant fields.

Progress by M18: No mailing list has been used until now to promote project results. Nevertheless, we intend

³⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

³⁶ <http://www.wupperinst.org/>

³⁷ <http://www.e3modelling.com>

³⁸ <https://iiasa.ac.at/>

³⁹ <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/index.aspx>

⁴⁰ <https://www.iccs.gr/en/institute-of-communication-and-computer-systems/>

⁴¹ www.holisticsa.gr

⁴² <https://www.uni-kassel.de/uni/en/>

⁴³ <https://www.tsinghua.edu.cn/en/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.chemeng.tsinghua.edu.cn/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.dess.tsinghua.edu.cn/en/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.ruc.edu.cn/>

⁴⁷ <https://en.sdu.edu.cn/>

⁴⁸ <https://en.chinacoal.com/>

⁴⁹ <https://arims.bit.edu.cn/>

⁵⁰ http://www.mglip.com/en/introduction_lab_en.html

⁵¹ <https://me-english.bit.edu.cn/>

⁵² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-china-bridge/posts/?feedView=all&viewAsMember=true>

⁵³ <https://enb.iisd.org/email/>

to send soon the WP3 technology inventories to the IAMC newsletter/ mailing list and follow up with more relevant content in the future. Additionally, mailing lists and newsletters such as the one from Carbon Brief⁵⁴ are used to follow relevant news about the decarbonisation in the EU and China.

4.9 Co-creation Workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues

Stakeholder engagement forms the backbone of all project activities and take the form of in-depth Co-creation Workshops (WP1) with small groups of stakeholders (~10-40 participants each) to discuss key issues related to the specific research topics and validate findings (~50-80 participants each). In addition, larger Stakeholder Dialogues (Task 7.2) are organised to disseminate the project's findings. Audiences include government officials and other policymakers from the EU and China, industrial representatives and associations (e.g., the World steel association, CEFIC), and international organisations (e.g., IEA, Energy Foundation China). Consortium partners are also linked to the EU-China flagship initiative on Climate Change and Biodiversity which will form a source of potential stakeholders. Stakeholders already expressed their strong support for the EU-CHINA BRIDGE project through Letters of Intent (Thyssenkrupp, COVESTRO, World Steel Association), informal exchange (BASF, China Energy Reserve and Chemicals Group Company, China Energy Investment,), and acting as project partners in China (China National Coal Group Corporation, Inner Mongolia Fulong Heating Engineering Technology). All stakeholder engagement activities are fully GDPR-compliant, and participants will be invited to follow the project in social media and subscribe in our newsletter.

Progress by M18: In the context of the 1st EU-China Stakeholder Dialogue, a discussion on Chinese steel decarbonisation roadmaps took place in Jiaying, China⁵⁵ (see Figure 6 for an indicative photo). Future events in the context of this Stakeholder Dialogue also include an EU-China exchange on CBAM implications and other international cooperation mechanisms on industrial decarbonization, an EU-China workshop on chemical defossilisation (including chemical recycling upscaling), and an EU-China workshop on the steel roadmap (including H₂ DRI steel).

Figure 6. Photo from the first event of the EU-China Stakeholder Dialogue

⁵⁴ <https://www.carbonbrief.org>

⁵⁵ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/news-events/forging-greener-steel-future-key-takeaways-eu-china-stakeholder-exchange-steel>

In terms of stakeholder co-creation on the EU side, three workshops have been organised by September 2025 (Table 6).

Table 6. Co-creation workshops in the EU

Events	Date	Participants
Co-Creation Workshop for scaling-up paths of specific technology options (Step 1)	Due: March 2025 <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scaling Pathways for Green Steelmaking in Europe with Hydrogen Direct Reduction of Iron Ore – Online Workshop, 15 external participants ⁵⁶. 2. Scaling Pathways for Chemical Recycling in Europe – Six expert interviews with stakeholders from Germany (4) and the Netherlands (2) 	In total: 21 participants from companies, industry associations, think tanks and research institutes
Implementing co-creation workshops for developing net-zero sectoral emission pathways	Due: April 2025 Stakeholder Workshop on decarbonisation scenarios for the EU	In total: 18 participants from services of the European commission, research institutes international institutions, and think tanks
Co-Creation Workshop for scaling-up paths of specific technology options (Step 2)	Due: September 2025 <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upscaling Pathways for Green Steelmaking in Europe with Hydrogen Direct Reduction of Iron Ore – Four external participants 2. Upscaling Pathways for Pyrolysis for Chemical Recycling in Europe – Eight external participants 	In total: 12 participants from companies, industry associations, think tanks and research institutes

On the Chinese side, two stakeholder co-creation field trips were organised for demonstration and scaling up hydrogen-based green methanol production. In July 2025, Chinese researchers, together with stakeholders, assessed construction progress, identified potential technical challenges, and clarified key definitions, including “green methanol.” In September 2025, the researchers and stakeholders jointly addressed the identified technical issues and conducted a collaborative technical feasibility assessment. Additionally, two major stakeholder co-creation activities were undertaken for demonstration and scaling up Integrated Waste Heat Utilisation (IWHU). In June 2024, the team conducted on-site investigations of the IWHU pilot project in Chifeng, Inner Mongolia, engaging with local partners to discuss technical issues related to pilot implementation. In February 2025, the team visited two completed projects in Shandong Province and held discussions with the involved companies to identify key barriers to scaling up IWHU deployment in China.

⁵⁶ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/news-events/workshop-report-scaling-pathways-green-steelmaking-europe>

4.10 Capacity building and training events

In the context of Task 7.5, yearly training events will be organised to promote data sharing and model co-development between the two regions and provide hand-on training on the use of models, datasets, technology roadmaps and other outcomes of the project. The events will be promoted to members of the scientific community in both Europe and China that work on topics related to climate change mitigation, energy, industrial ecology, land use, air pollution, etc. The IAM PARIS platform will play a pivotal role for sharing model documentation and provide interactive interfaces to access and visualise all modelling results for the decarbonisation pathways produced in the project.

Progress by M18: As shown in Table 7, 2 IAM Capacity Building workshops have already taken place in the context of the annual general meetings of the project, while a third one is planned for February 2027. Our website provides more information about the first⁵⁷ and second⁵⁸ workshop, while an indicative photo is shown below in Figure 7.

Table 7. Planning of IAM Capacity Building events

Events	Date	Participants
IAM Capacity Building I	Done: 29.10.2025	Partner Institutes+
IAM Capacity Building II	Done: 9.9.2025	Partner Institutes+
IAM Capacity Building III	Planned: February 2027	Partner Institutes+

Figure 7. Photo from the first IAM Capacity Building workshop in Weihai

4.11 Scientific conferences

EU-CHINA BRIDGE partners will participate in scientific conferences to disseminate the project results to the

⁵⁷ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/news-events/integrated-model-development-capacity-building-workshop>

⁵⁸ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/news-events/eu-china-bridge-general-assembly-athens-2025>

scientific community. Additionally, conferences will be used to monitor relevant research in climate-economy modelling, industrial ecology, and other relevant topics. The following conferences have been assessed as relevant to the project: Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium (IAMC)⁵⁹, European Climate + Energy Modelling Platform (ECEMP)⁶⁰, International Energy Workshop⁶¹, Energy Modeling Forum⁶², Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES) conference⁶³, Earth System Governance annual conference⁶⁴.

Progress by M18: The following conference presentations had acknowledged the project:

- Shan, Y. (2025). Global methane footprints growth and drivers 1990-2023. 31st International Input-Output Association Conference (IIOA)
- Hullman, C. (2025). Navigating the Plastics Industry Towards Low Environmental Impact – A Comparative Policy Analysis of Germany and Italy. 16th International Sustainability Transitions (IST) Conference 2025.

Future conference participations will be directly added on the website⁶⁵.

4.12 Policy conferences

Along the duration of EU-CHINA BRIDGE from April 2024 to March 2027, three sessions of the UNFCCC's Conference of the Parties (COP) will take place. These conferences offer great opportunities to reach out to policymakers, NGOs, industrialists, scientists, and other audiences and promote the project. In terms of European-specific conferences, the European Sustainable Development Week⁶⁶ and the European Sustainable Energy Week⁶⁷ will be policy-relevant fora for presenting the project's results. The project's CDE team will be also in contact with the Chinese partners in order to add here relevant policy conferences in China.

Progress by M18: Since the main project results are expected during the second half of the project, we have not yet presented any findings at a policy conference. Nevertheless, we are planning to apply for a policy session at the upcoming European Sustainable Energy Week on industrial decarbonisation along with the Horizon Europe projects ENTICE⁶⁸ and TRANSIENCE⁶⁹.

4.13 Synergies

Synergies with relevant projects can increase the outreach potential of the project's outputs and raise awareness among a broad spectrum of stakeholders. The CDE team will contact projects of interest and co-organise synergetic activities such as participating in each other's events, developing synergetic publications, and cross-disseminating information and outputs through social media and project websites. Indicative

⁵⁹ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/annual-meetings/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.ecemf.eu/ecemp/european-climate-and-energy-modelling-platform/>

⁶¹ <https://www.internationalenergyworkshop.org>

⁶² <https://emf.stanford.edu>

⁶³ <https://www.sdewes.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.earthssystemgovernance.org/annual-conferences/>

⁶⁵ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/publications/conferences>

⁶⁶ <https://esdw.eu>

⁶⁷ https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en

⁶⁸ <https://enticeproject.eu>

⁶⁹ <https://www.transience.eu>

projects for CDE synergies that will run (fully or partly) in parallel with EU-CHINA BRIDGE include the following:

- DIAMOND (HEU): Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development⁷⁰
- IAM COMPACT (HEU): Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling: Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action⁷¹
- TRANSIENCE (HEU): TRANSItioning towards an Efficient, carbon-Neutral Circular European industry⁷²

It is noted that these projects are mainly suggested in terms of CDE collaborations. In terms of progressing scientific knowledge in the climate-economy field, EU-CHINA BRIDGE will also collaborate with other ongoing projects and initiatives such as the IN₄climate and NRW initiative, Global Steel Transformation, and the Horizon Europe EU-CIP. Additionally, EU-CHINA BRIDGE will be based on previous projects such as CEADS, H2020 NDC ASPECTS, H2020 ENGAGE, and H2020 ForestNavigator.

Progress by M18: As shown in Table 8 below, we have jointly published two papers with other Horizon Europe projects. Additionally, we are planning to have a joint event with ENTICE and TRANSIENCE projects, as mentioned in the previous section.

Table 8. Synergies with other projects

Activity	Name	Synergy
Joint paper	Shan et al. (2025). Global methane footprints growth and drivers 1990-2023. <i>Nature Communications</i> , 16(1), 8184. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-63383-5	PANTHEON (HEU) ⁷³
Joint paper	Hartvig et al. (2025). Comparing economic impacts of net-zero transition with climate damage uncertainties using a dual-model approach. <i>Environmental Research: Energy</i> , 2(3), 035005. https://doi.org/10.1088/2753-3751/ade5e	ENTICE (HEU), PRISMA (HEU), ECEMF (HEU)

⁷⁰ <https://climate-diamond.eu>

⁷¹ <https://www.iam-compact.eu>

⁷² <https://www.transience.eu>

⁷³

5 Communication materials

From the onset of the project, we have developed a visual identity to encapsulate the main characteristics of EU-CHINA BRIDGE and effectively communicate them to all relevant stakeholders. This visual identity was then used to develop a project logo, a branding guide (including colours, fonts etc.), and tailor-made templates for Microsoft PowerPoint and Word. Furthermore, several promotional materials have been developed to communicate the scope and objectives of the project, such as posters, flyers, and an institutional presentation. More such materials will be developed in the project, along with videos and infographics, to present the results and main findings of the projects. All promotional materials and visual identity will be uploaded to the website in a respective webpage.

5.1 Visual identity and communication package

5.1.1 Logo

EU-CHINA BRIDGE mainly aims to bring together modelling experts and stakeholders from the EU and China to jointly advancing technology innovations roadmaps and decarbonisation pathways for both regions, focusing especially on energy-intensive industries. The visual identity was designed to be inclusive of all partners and audiences in both China and Europe, also considering cultural differences in terms of colours, symbols, and layout. The name of the project was the primary inspiration for the logo and the visual identity that is based on the main flag colours for the two regions, that is the blue from the EU flag and the red from the flag of the People's Republic of China. A red and blue bridge-like symbol is used to further express the connection between the two regions while a sans serif font (Geometra Rounded) is used to express clarity and transparency in this connection. Similarly, the sans serif font Corbel is used for all other project text, as it was designed specifically for clarity on the screen, even at small display sizes.

The logo that was developed and used for the project can be seen in Figure 8. Figure 9 showcases other alternatives that were created and considered along with the project consortium during the first month of the project. The rest of the visual identity shown below is based on the colours and characteristics of the logo. Further visual elements will be also developed in the future with the same visual identity such as icons and glyphs. The logo as well as other visual identity materials (i.e., Word & PowerPoint templates) have been already evaluated by the coordinators and the project consortium to ensure that it is attractive for all parties.

Figure 8. Project logo

Figure 9. Alternative logos created during the initial elaboration of the project’s visual identity

5.1.2 Templates

Throughout the duration of EU-CHINA BRIDGE, there will be a variety of documents circulated among partners, disseminated to stakeholders, published on social media, or printed and shared at events. In order to consolidate the project’s visual identity and ensure uniformity and recognisability, specific templates have been created for each Microsoft Word and for PowerPoint using the same colours and styles across all material. The Word template is showcased in the current document while an example of the PowerPoint template can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Project presentation template

5.1.3 Visual identity for social media

Social media will be an important outlet for the project’s communication efforts. Based on the visual identity above, headers have been developed for all social media accounts of the project in X (Figure 11), LinkedIn, and BlueSky. Headers for other social media (e.g., WeChat for the Chinese side) will be developed upon request. Additionally, ad-hoc visual material will be developed to accompany social media posts in the future.

Figure 11. Social media header for the project's account in X

5.1.4 Flyer

A promotional flyer has been developed giving general information and creating visibility about the project (Figure 12). It has been primarily produced in English and will be translated into Chinese in the future. As with all communication package items, the flyer will be available online on the project website and will be downloaded and printed only when needed, e.g., for events and conferences about the project.

Figure 12. Project flyer

5.1.5 Leaflet

EU-CHINA BRIDGE has also produced a promotional 3-fold leaflet featuring a short project description along with concise descriptions of the project's motivation, objectives, project partners, and contact information (Figure 13). Along with the flyer, the leaflet is intended for project promotion at conferences and other events and will be only printed when needed.

Figure 13. 3-fold leaflet with information about the project

5.1.6 Poster and roll-up banner

For further establishing the project identity in major events that EU-CHINA BRIDGE organises or participates, we have developed a project poster in A3 and Ao sizes and a roll-up poster (Figure 14). The poster can be used in online poster exhibitions or printed for physical events while the roll-up banner will be mainly reserved in high-exposure events and will be printed when needed.

Figure 14. Project poster in A3 and Ao (left) and roll-up banner (right)

5.2 Communication means

5.2.1 Newsletter

The newsletter's goal is to periodically inform interested stakeholders about the project's progress. A regular electronic newsletter will be issued providing information on the project at least four times per year. The newsletter will incorporate inputs from all partners on the progress and key outcomes of the project, including recent deliverables, scientific publications, event participations, infographics, videos, and other materials developed by the project. The newsletter may also include news about other research activities that are relevant to the project, such as updates from other projects with similar topics (e.g., climate-economy modelling, industrial decarbonisation) as well as news related to EU-China collaborations on climate and industrial topics.

In compliance with the GDPR, a person will be included on the newsletter mailing list only if one is informed and explicit consent has been given, while the possibility of withdrawing the consent is clearly explained. Consent will be provided either by filling out an online subscription form or by direct email in case of personal contacts. In addition, the newsletter will provide dedicated dissemination for the Chinese partners, promoting their publications and project-relevant work to ensure visibility and recognition within the wider stakeholder community.

Progress by M18: Two newsletters have been published by September 2025, sent to 346 recipients in LinkedIn and MailerLite (target by end of project: 3000), and achieving a 59% opening rate (target: 30%). The newsletters can be seen on the website⁷⁴ and our LinkedIn group⁷⁵, while a screenshot can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Screenshot from project newsletter

⁷⁴ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/communication/newsletters-press-releases>

⁷⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/newsletters/eu-china-bridge-newsletter-7311336947908591617/>

5.2.2 Scientific publications

Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and building scientific credibility for the project's work. At least 15 scientific articles will be published in open-access, high-quality, peer-reviewed journals. Journals also offering open peer review, such as Open Research Europe, will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of participating organisations. Access to papers and supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated project OpenAIRE/Zenodo community, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability. Moreover, the WP7 team will use its social media channels to promote the articles.

Progress by M18: Four scientific articles have been published acknowledging project funding, while three other articles are in preparation. The published articles are shown on our website⁷⁶ and in the list below.

1. Shan, Y., Tian, K., Li, R., Guan, Y., Ou, J., Guan, D., & Hubacek, K. (2025). Global methane footprints growth and drivers 1990-2023. *Nature Communications*, 16(1), 8184. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-63383-5>
2. Hartvig, A. D., Simo, M., Fazekas, D., Fragkos, P., Fragkiadakis, K., Fragkiadakis, D., & Vrontisi, Z. (2025). Comparing economic impacts of net-zero transition with climate damage uncertainties using a dual-model approach. *Environmental Research: Energy*, 2(3), 035005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2753-3751/ade5e>
3. Wang, J., Shan, Y., Xu, J., Li, R., Zhao, C., & Wang, S. (2024). Consumption-Based Emissions of African Countries: An Analysis of Decoupling Dynamics and Drivers. *Earth's Future*, 12(11), e2024EF005008. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024EF005008>
4. Liu, B., Shan, Y., Kuik, R., Ji, X., Chapungu, L., Yang, X., & Hubacek, K. (2024). The landscape of city-level GHG emission accounts in Africa. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 28(6), 1377–1391. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13562>

It is noted that several other publications have been submitted by the Chinese side of the project, as shown in the list below. Since the Chinese researchers only acknowledge the Chinese funding number, they are not counted against our KPI of 15 papers by the end of the project. Still, they provide an indication of the parallel work that has been informed by the EU-China discussions during the project.

- Ke, P., Ciais, P., Sitch, S., Li, W., Bastos, A., Liu, Z., Xu, Y., Gui, X., Bian, J., Goll, D. S., Xi, Y., Li, W., O'Sullivan, M., Gonçalves de Souza, J., Friedlingstein, P., & Chevallier, F. (2024). Low latency carbon budget analysis reveals a large decline of the land carbon sink in 2023. *National Science Review*, 11(12), nwae367. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwae367>
- Wu, S., Shao, Z., Andrew, R.M. et al. Global CO₂ uptake by cement materials accounts 1930–2023. *Sci Data* 11, 1409 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-04234-8>
- Kong, H., Sun, Y., Wang, H., Wang, J., Sun, L., & Shen, J. (2024). Life cycle assessment of ammonia co-firing power plants: A comprehensive review and analysis from a whole industrial chain perspective. *Advances in Applied Energy*, 14, 100178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adapen.2024.100178>

⁷⁶ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/publications/scientific-publications>

- Wang, Z., Sun, Y., Kong, H., & Xia-Bauer, C. (2025). An in-depth review of key technologies and pathways to carbon neutrality: Classification and assessment of decarbonisation technologies. *Carbon Neutrality*, 4, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43979-025-00129-8>

5.2.3 Policy briefs

Apart from inviting policymakers to the co-creation events, we will promote our project results through 12 policy briefs. The policy briefs will be developed based on the work of WPs 3, 4, and 6 and will provide relevant and actionable recommendations for directly informing policy in China and the EU based on our project results, considering policy cycles and relevant opportunities (e.g., revised NECPs in 2025, updated NDCs of China and the EU, long-term strategies before 2028). The briefs will be disseminated during the Stakeholder Dialogues and promoted through the project website and social media and summarised in media articles.

Progress by M18: No policy briefs have been published by now. All of them are expected during the second project period.

5.2.4 Blog posts and media articles

Articles on selected results of the project will be published in leading media websites and blogs will be disseminated via the promotional channels identified in Section 4.1. In addition, findings and insights from internal workshops will be published in the form of blog posts or short articles, providing accessible reflections on the project's discussions and intermediate results. All partners will support this process by suggesting media contacts and extending the list of interesting media targets. At least five media articles are expected to be published in the project's course.

Progress by M18: Three blog items have been already published on the project website⁷⁷ covering different project activities until now. Figure 16 shows an example from a blog item that details some of the results of the EU workshop on steel decarbonisation. More blog items are planned in the future and are expected to be converted to media articles as well.

⁷⁷ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/news-events>

Figure 16. Indicative screenshot from a blog post

5.2.5 Videos and infographics

The WP7 team will produce videos and infographics to create awareness with the project and promote project results, especially among policymakers, industry representatives, and other non-academic stakeholders. At least five videos and five infographics will be developed throughout the project's duration and will be promoted on the project website, social media, newsletter, and other potential outlets.

Progress by M18: All videos and infographics will be prepared during the second half of the project where the main project results will become available.

6 Overview of current progress and next steps

As shown in the previous sections, several communication and dissemination activities have taken place by September 2025 (Month 18). During the first 18 months of the project we have developed the website, established the visual identity, promoted the project in social media, created blogposts, and published the initial project outputs as four scientific publications, while organising several workshops for stakeholder engagement and capacity development. Nevertheless, the bulk of CDE activities will come towards the second half of the project, where most of the key exploitable results of the project are expected to be released. This is also reflected to our progress towards the communication and dissemination KPIs that have been set at the outset of EU-CHINA BRIDGE (Section 2). As shown on Table 9 and 10, the target on the visual identity has been already reached, while there is already progress towards our targets for social media, newsletters, scientific outreach, media articles/blog items, and synergies with other projects. Conversely, we will need to strengthen our efforts in all other metrics by promoting our project website to increase its visitors and by developing more infographics, videos, policy briefs, and content for the IAM PARIS platform.

Table 9. Progress on communication KPIs

Activity	KPI target	Progress by September 2025
Visual identity	All materials will be published on the project website	All materials already published ⁷⁸ .
Project website	2000 unique visitors/year 30% of return visitors	~400 unique visitors within the last 12 months ~10% of return visitors
Social media	1,000 uses of EU-CHINA BRIDGE hashtag or handle 500 followers on LinkedIn/X 1000 on WeChat	105 uses of hashtag/handle (incl. reposts); 520 interactions in LinkedIn (likes and reposts) 304 followers on LinkedIn, 137 on X, 624 on BlueSky
Newsletters (four per year)	3000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate	346 recipients in LinkedIn and MailerLite 59% opening rate
Infographics & videos	>1,000 views/downloads	Not relevant yet
Media articles	At least 5 articles	3 blogposts created on the project website

Table 10. Progress on dissemination KPIs

Activity	KPIs	Progress by September 2025
Enhanced IAM PARIS platform	2000 unique users/year 30% of return visitors	1 project workspace created on Technology Inventories; no monitoring of IAM PARIS platform yet.

⁷⁸ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu/communication/visual-identity>

Policy briefs	12 policy briefs	Not relevant yet
Scientific outreach	> 15 papers; > 6 conferences	4 papers published/accepted; 3 in preparation 2 conference presentations (IST 2025, IIOA 2025)
Networking activities with relevant EU and Chinese projects	Project referenced in 10 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	1 joint paper with PRISMA, ECCEF, ENTICE 1 joint paper with PANTHEON

Based on this evaluation of the current CDE performance of the project, the following next steps are suggested:

1. Promote our website through social media (e.g., by sharing links of news and events), webinars (e.g., by enabling webinar registrations through the website), and policy events (e.g., by providing more interesting content for the website).
2. Develop a dedicated section on the website to showcase Chinese partners' contributions and disseminate their publications and project-relevant work.
3. Publish short blog posts or media articles summarising key insights from internal workshops, highlighting progress and lessons learned in an accessible way. Promote them through social media, media outlets, and other project networks.
4. Establish a content dissemination tracker to better coordinate contributions from all partners, ensuring timely and diverse communication outputs.
5. Pilot the use of infographics and short video explainers to make technical content accessible to expert and non-expert audiences.
6. Create policy briefs and promote them through social media, policy conferences and other relevant events.
7. Upload more results from EU-CHINA BRIDGE to the IAM PARIS platform (e.g., WP4 Policy Inventories)
8. Create more synergies with other projects (e.g., joint event on EUSEW 2025 and more joint papers)

More steps will be considered in an ad-hoc basis throughout the next project year in order to improve progress towards the CDE KPIs. Lastly, with the support of the project coordinator (WI), the CDE team will align with the Chinese partners to further explore potential CDE activities that can be implemented in China.